

INVESTMENT CLIMATE AND ANALYSIS OF MODERN MECHANISMS FOR FINANCING INVESTMENT PROJECTS

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Abstract. The investment climate is one of the decisive factors influencing the competitiveness and sustainable growth of national economies. In recent years, Uzbekistan has undertaken extensive reforms aimed at liberalizing its economy, attracting foreign direct investment (FDI), and modernizing financial institutions. This paper examines the development of Uzbekistan's investment climate and provides a comprehensive analysis of modern mechanisms for financing investment projects. Particular attention is paid to government reforms, the role of international financial institutions, public-private partnerships (PPPs), and innovative financial instruments such as project financing, green bonds, and venture capital. The study concludes that the success of investment policy depends on improving institutional frameworks, ensuring financial security, and strengthening investor confidence. Practical recommendations are offered to expand financing opportunities for both domestic and foreign investors in Uzbekistan's rapidly transforming economy.

Keywords: investment climate, sustainable economic growth, foreign direct investment inflows, mechanisms for financing investment projects.

Investment plays a vital role in accelerating economic growth, enhancing industrial competitiveness, and creating sustainable employment opportunities. For transition economies like Uzbekistan, the establishment of a favorable investment climate is essential for integrating into global markets and ensuring long-term development. Over the past decade, Uzbekistan has made significant progress in improving its investment environment through legal reforms, liberalization of currency exchange, simplification of tax administration, and infrastructure modernization.

However, despite notable achievements, challenges remain. These include limited diversification of financing mechanisms, relatively high investment risks, and the need for greater integration of innovative financial instruments. Therefore, analyzing the development of Uzbekistan's investment climate and the effectiveness of modern financing mechanisms is critical for strengthening investor confidence and ensuring efficient capital mobilization.

The concept of the investment climate is broadly defined in economic literature as the combination of institutional, economic, legal, and social conditions that influence investment decisions (World Bank, 2020). According to

Kuznetsov (2019), countries with stable macroeconomic environments and transparent legal systems attract higher levels of investment. For developing economies, the availability of financing mechanisms is equally important, as limited access to capital can constrain investment flows (Aslund, 2018).

Recent studies highlight the increasing role of innovative financing tools. Project financing, which separates investment risk from sponsors' balance sheets, has gained importance in infrastructure development (Esty, 2020). Similarly, green bonds and sustainable financing instruments are becoming popular due to global climate commitments (OECD, 2021). Public-private partnerships (PPPs) have also proven effective in mobilizing private sector resources for large-scale investment projects (Grimsey & Lewis, 2017).

For Uzbekistan, research shows that reforms have improved the ease of doing business, but further measures are required to reduce bureaucratic barriers and enhance investor protection (ADB, 2022). This underscores the need for diversified financing mechanisms that align with both global practices and local conditions.

Foreign experts emphasize that in order to achieve the Sustainable Development Goals until 2030, developed in 2015 by the UN General Assembly as a "plan to achieve a better and more sustainable future for all", it is necessary to invest in production capacities. Investments are one of the main drivers designed to increase the financial stability of the national economy, its competitiveness, ensure expanded reproduction, allow for the development of advanced technologies, contribute to the development and creation of innovative products, give impetus to the development of knowledge-intensive sectors of the economy, reduce unemployment, improve the well-being of the population as a whole and achieve economic growth. In the modern economy of Uzbekistan, there are a number of problems associated with attracting investment resources, including foreign direct investment. Among the above-mentioned: poor infrastructure development, insufficient funding, lack of conditions for attracting investment in the development and implementation of innovative ideas and technologies, lack of advertising of investment attractiveness in the countries of the world community, a high level of differentiation in the distribution of investments between regions, etc. All this confirms the need for further improvement of mechanisms for financing investment projects in the Republic of Uzbekistan and determines the relevance and significance of this study.

In the sustainable development of the textile industry of Uzbekistan, the goal of which the government sees as the accelerated development of the country's economy, an important role is played by cotton-textile clusters created in various regions of the country. Cotton-textile clusters include profitable production chains where raw cotton is processed and turned into a textile product. Cotton-textile clusters unite various enterprises of the industry into a single whole, promote joint work of enterprises, exchange of experience and technology, as well as joint investments. The dynamics of the development of cotton-textile clusters is steadily growing: in 2022, cotton-textile clusters of Uzbekistan operated in 86 regions of the country.

The creation of cotton-textile clusters influences the strategy of attracting investment by stimulating private investment in the cotton value chain. The activities of cotton-textile clusters allow optimizing the structure of sources of funds by developing financing within the cluster.

Since cotton-textile clusters in all regions of Uzbekistan produce products for export, they are forced to improve the quality of their products and introduce innovations in order to meet international standards, which increases their attractiveness for investment.

The export orientation of the cotton-textile clusters of Uzbekistan is a determining factor in the formation of an investment strategy, as it creates additional opportunities for growth, stability and long-term relations with investors.

The main types of manufactured products: knitted fabric, cotton fabrics, hosiery, garments and knitwear. World Bank experts note that "cotton-textile clusters should give priority to investments in their core business - the production and processing of cotton. They were created to benefit both cotton producers and processors." .

Traditionally, the sufficiently high development of the sewing and textile industry of Uzbekistan contributes to the creation of such a form of production organization as cotton-textile clusters, which include all links in the technological chain of textile production: from cotton cultivation to the sale of finished products. The inclusion of agricultural enterprises in cotton-textile clusters contributes to the diversification of agriculture, during which cotton yields increase, and the area of its crops decreases throughout the country. In this regard, the cluster can be considered as a center for investment and innovation, designed to stimulate the development of the domestic economy.

Joint activities of enterprises within the cotton-textile cluster contribute to the emergence of a synergistic effect, since in the implementation of production activities, enterprises exchange technologies and innovative ideas in joint scientific and production activities, which enhances the competitiveness of cluster enterprises.

The creation of clusters is considered by the government of Uzbekistan as an incentive to develop the textile industry more evenly throughout the territory of Uzbekistan. The task under consideration requires a significant amount of investment.

Based on the calculations, it can be concluded that the most significant risks for each type of financing for textile industry projects in Uzbekistan are different:

- for FDI financing, the most significant are a decrease in the country's credit rating, insufficient financing, and changes in the investment climate;

- for financing fixed capital investments, the most significant are: the risk of non-recoupment of investments, lack of enterprises' own funds, and a decrease in the country's credit rating;

- when financing PPP investments, the most significant risks are: ineffective interaction between the public and private sectors, ineffective financial management, changes in investment and property legislation;

- when financing investments in the banking sector, the most significant risks are: borrower default, reduction in bank profits, fluctuations in securities and exchange rates.

There are also general risks for all types of financing for textile industry investments: rising inflation, geopolitical instability, and unfavorable conditions in external commodity markets.

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